

EMBRACING GLOBAL COMPACT BY MANAGEMENT EDUCATION- A MANIFEST CONTENT ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Objectives-To assess the contrasts of revealed actions in the commitment letter among the management institutions participated to espouse the principles of PRME; To describe the direction of initiatives and to detect the ties of action lines to fulfill the principles manifested by PRME commitment documents of selected 45 numbers of member institutions of select management institutions of the globe; To compares the incorporation of paired actions (variables) manifested by the PRME commitment documents of select institutes around the globe.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-A manifest content analysis itself is a qualitative research based on content analysis and review. This paper reviews the initiatives adopted by different management institution in different countries for pursuing the principles given by united nation global compact for a sustainable and inclusive socio-economic development. It also makes a comparative study of some action instigated and put into practice for the global responsiveness of management institutes.

Findings-The manifested content analysis on the commitment of PRME participants illuminates many interesting facts. The ties of simultaneous manifested action ties in case of industry instate interaction and curricula change is a global phenomenon in the context of management institutes

Limitations-Contents analysis is an advanced qualitative research techniques. Today many studies on these lines are using the advanced content analysis software. This study suffers limitations of small sample i.e. only contents of 45 documents are analyzed, where as a global study can be conducted on whole PRME commitment documents.

Practical implications- All these interesting findings manifested content analysis of documents can serve as the basis for further exploration at country level as well as global level

Originality/Value-Study on manifest contents analysis is rare next to nothing in management literatures. Study on global compact their commitment manifestation is first of its kind.

Key words: Management education, Sustainability, UNGC, PRME, CSR, Line of Actions, Content Analysis

Introduction

Management students are the future business and social leaders. They will hold the key to direct the trade and commerce which will influence the socio-economic state of affairs significantly. This rat racing system induces the management institutions to manufacture thousands of wealth generators instead of a responsible business leader. To meet the demand of wealth generation the management students fail to inherit the humanitarian features for being a most valuable part of a sustainable and inclusive socio-economic development with ecological sustainability.

Sometimes they don't even hesitate to adopt unprincipled policies and compensate through CSR. To combat this situation PRME was developed between October 2006 and July 2007 by an international task force of 60 Deans and university presidents as well as scholars committed to the idea of responsible management education. To enhance the multi-stakeholder nature of the development process, the drafting of the principles was supported by representatives from the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC), the Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB), the Aspen Institute's Business and Society Program, the European Foundation for Management Development (EFMD), the Globally Responsible Leadership Initiative (GRLI), Net Impact, a student organization with more than 13,000 members, the Graduate Management Admission Council (GMAC), and the European Academy of Business in Society (EABIS). All of these institutions remain as the partners of the initiative as they are members of the steering committee which guides the PRME. In July 2007, the outcome of this development process was presented to UN Secretary-General Ban Ki moon at the triennial Global Compact Leaders Summit in Geneva. PRME has introduced 6 principles and series of guidelines which articulates those are not only CSR or any Philanthropic attitude, at the end of business operation, but to ensure that no one should be the victim.

The 6 Principles of PMRE

Principle 1: Purpose: We will develop the capabilities of students to be future generators of sustainable value for business and society at large and to work for an inclusive and sustainable global economy.

Principle 2: Values: We will incorporate into our academic activities and curricula the values of global social responsibility as portrayed in international initiatives such as the United Nations Global Compact.

Principle 3: Method: We will create educational frameworks, materials, processes and environments that enable effective learning experiences for responsible leadership.

Principle 4: Research: We will engage in conceptual and empirical research that advances our understanding about the role, dynamics, and impact of corporations in the creation of sustainable social, environmental and economic value.

Principle 5: Partnership: We will interact with managers of business corporations to extend our knowledge of their challenges in meeting social and environmental responsibilities and to explore jointly effective approaches to meeting these challenges.

Principle 6: Dialogue: We will facilitate and support dialog and debate among educators, students, business, government, consumers, media, and civil society organizations and other interested groups and stakeholders on critical issues related to global social responsibility and sustainability.

Statement of Problem-The participating institutes and the universities no-doubt are committed to these 6-PRME principles. While from an observation on the PRME commitment letter drafted by the institutes and universities indicates their concentration only on the few issues. A brief reading of such letter PRME submitted by the participating institutes indicated that institutions are concentrating on the issue of innovation, curriculum change,

seminars, entrepreneurship, and finally, emphasis on the environment. As the 6-principles of PRME sound the critical aspects such as social, sustainability, environment, change, values and ethics, but, in contrast the participants' commitment to the cause stated in their letters and report are limited to issues. In this backdrop question can be raised whether all the institutes of management and university department or centre teaching management which are registered under the PRME are similar to each one? What are the contents of those submitted documents as the commitment that manifest as the supremacy of the global thinking by the management education under the PRME?

Review of literatures

Barman in his article "Social Responsibility of Management Teacher- Beyond Teaching" stated that management is a multidisciplinary subject, so the teachers need to adopt a holistic approach in teaching management curriculum in order to develop new managerial workforce which will influence business, society, technology and humanity. **French and Gray** (1996) in their book 'Rethinking Management Education' stated that the managerial competence obviously depends on managerial effectiveness related to management education, developed on the basis of mainstream research. **Dunne & Martin** (2006) in their article 'Design Thinking and How It Will Change Management Education: An Interview and Discussion' introduced the concept of design thinking and said that the students should be encouraged to think broadly and develop deep understanding of the problem and understand the value of contribution. **Baker D.F & Baker S.J** in their article, to "Catch the Sparkling Glow": A Canvas for Creativity in the Management Classroom, wrote that the business leaders necessitate to have creativity and innovations in order to combat with present challenges but the present classroom practice within the business school does not necessarily encourage management students to think creatively, so that innovation may be obtained. **Barman** in his article, "Management of Socially Relevant Quality of Higher Education- Do Indian Institutions Care It", said that higher education should have to responsibility by generating socially responsive knowledge through absorbing socially responsive values and practices and innovation is a key factor in this process. **Samuelson** (2003) in his key note address at AACSB international Deans Conference said that not only strong morality, a management student must have foresight, creative problem solving ability, leadership, deep listening and negotiation skill and an understanding of the social context, can navigate towards the better world. **Sweetea. & Kumar. M.** (2011), in their article, "Management Education in India: Issues and Challenges" said that Management education is facing the crisis of significance at the present situation. Now they need to rejuvenate management education in order to meet the expectation of the students, faculty, society, industry, Government and global community at a large. "**HEC Paris 2010 Social Business/ Enterprise & Poverty Certificate Project**" (2010) stated that educational issues are important human and social development, and healthy economical growth which are the driver of long term wellbeing. The report on "*the Principles of Responsible Management Education* (2007)" says that academic institutions help shape the behavior and attitude of the business leaders through management education, research and other academic development program. It further added that the management institutions can bring a constructive wave of positive change which ensures a holistic development for both corporate and society.

Objectives of the study- The main objectives of the study are-

- To assess the contrasts of revealed actions in the commitment letter among the management institutions participated to espouse the principles of PRME
- To describe the direction of initiatives and to detect the ties of action lines to fulfill the principles manifested by PRME commitment documents of selected 45 numbers of member institutions of select management institutions of the globe.
- To compare the distributions of paired actions (variables) manifested by the PRME commitment documents of select institutes around the globe.

Methodology

The paper is mainly based on qualitative research design. For synthesis the research the present paper would pursue the manifest content analysis. This analysis describes the observed aspects of communications of the PRME documents via objective, systematic, and empirical means (Onwuegbuzie. and et.al., 2012). PRME participant management educational institutions under United Nations Global Compact submitted commitment letters to the PRME repositories. The data has been downloaded and documents were readout thoroughly and consciously to find out the actions line described in the documents. These actions lines have been arranged for content analysis on the basis of contents stated in the commitments. The available contents were assigned binary number format (**0- Non availability/non adaptation, 1-Adoptation/Available**) thus transformed the descriptive manifested contents to manifested numbers. 45 numbers of documents (10 Brazilian universities, 10 Indian, 10 US Universities and Institutions, 10 from France, and 5 Japanese universities and institutions,) were analyzed to synthesize the line of actions undertaken under mandate of PRME and principle. The action lines of these selected institutes were analyzed horizontal line of action and then vertical line of action. Later all the lines of actions of the selected and examined jointly to draw contrasted overview of the actions to know the trends of application of PRME guideline.

Scope and Significance

This study is limited to some of PRME related initiative and actions like change, adoption and innovation in curricula, CSR of Management institutions to society and environment etc. The study is limited to few management institutions (50 institutions from 5 countries) around the world for a limited period only.

Country wise Contents Supremacy Analysis

Table no- 1

Country- Brazil	Change in curricula			University- industry interface(partnership)		Corporate Social responsibility	
	innovation	Change	adoption	seminar	entrepreneurship	To society	To environment
University name							
1.	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
2.	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
3.	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
4.	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
5.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
6.	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
7.	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
8.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
9.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
10.	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
Contents Manifestation	70%	20%	100%	100%	70%	100%	70%

Table no-1 represents the line of action of some selected activities adopted by few of the selected Brazilian management institutes to pursue PRME principles. Through horizontal analysis in case of **change in curricula** we can find that in integrating three sub action(innovation, change & adoption) , only two institutes (no-1 & no-8) integrated all three, five institutes adopted (no-4,5,6,7 & 9) adopted two actions and three institutes adopted only one action. Whereas in **University- industry interface (partnership)** it states that seven institutes (no- 3,4,5,6,7,8

&9) incorporated two actions and three institutes(no- 1,2 & 10) implemented only one action. Similarly for **Corporate Social responsibility** seven institutes (1,2,3,5,8,9&10) incorporated two actions whereas three institutes incorporated only one action (no- 4,6 & 7). Through vertical analysis of actions, it can be assumed that only one among selected Brazilian management institutes integrated all seven actions (studied here), three institutes (1,5 & 9) adopted six actions, four institutes (3,4,6 & 7) commenced five actions, two institutes (2 & 10) adopted four actions in order to follow PRME guidelines as participants.

Name of Universities

1. Faculdade de Engenharia e Inovacao Tecnico Profissional, Brazil
2. Faculdade Maringá, Brazil
3. Antonio Meneghetti Faculdade, Brazil
4. Faculdades Integradas do Brasil – UniBrasil, Brazil
5. Escola Superior de Propaganda e Marketing, Brazil
6. Instituto de Tecnologia do Parana – TECPAR,Brazil,
7. Brazilian School of Public and Business Administration – EBAPE, Brazil
8. National Service of Industrial Apprentice of Parana - SENAI Parana, Brazil
9. Social Service of Industry of Parana - SESI Parana,Brazil
10. Universidade Positivo, Brazil

Table no-2 represents the line of action of some selected activities adopted by few of the selected Japanese management institutes to pursue PRME principles. Through horizontal analysis in case of **change in curricula** we can find that in integrating three sub action (innovation, change & adoption), only one institutes (no-2) integrated all thee, and four institutes adopted only one action. Whereas in **University- industry interface (partnership)**, it states that three institutes (no- 1, 2 &3) incorporated two actions and two institutes (no- 4 & 5) implemented only one action. Similarly for **Corporate Social responsibility** all five institutes (1,2,3,4 & 5) incorporated two actions.

Table no-2

Country- Japan	Change in curricula			University- industry interface(partnership)		Corporate Social responsibility	
	innovation	Change	adoption	seminar	entrepreneurship	To society	To environment
1.	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
2.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3.	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
4.	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
5.	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
Content Manifestation	20%	20%	100%	100%	60%	100%	100%

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Through vertical analysis of actions, it can be assumed that only one among selected Japanese management institute (no-2) integrated all seven actions (studied here), two institutes (1 & 3) commenced five actions and rest two institutes (4 & 5) adopted four actions in order to follow PRME guidelines as participants.

1. Global Security Research Institute, Japan
2. Nagoya University of Commerce and Business Graduate School, Japan
3. Graduate School of Management and Faculty of Management, Atomi University, Japan
4. Kwansei Gakuin University, Japan
5. Doshisha Business School, Japan

Table no-3 represents the line of action of some selected activities adopted by few of the selected management institutes from France to pursue PRME principles. During horizontal analysis in case of **change in curricula** we can find that in integrating three sub action (innovation, change & adoption) five out of five selected management institutes adopted two actions, Whereas in **University- industry interface (partnership)** it states that three institutes (no- 2,3 &5) incorporated two actions and two institutes (no- 1 & 4) implemented only one action. Likewise for **Corporate Social responsibility** four institutes (2, 3, 4& 5) incorporated two actions, whereas, one institutes (no- 1) incorporated only one action. Through vertical analysis of actions, it can be understood that three institutes (no- 2, 3 & 5) adopted six actions, one institutes (no-4) commenced five actions and one institutes (no-1) adopted four actions in order to follow PRME guidelines of 10 participants.

Table no-3

Country- France	Change in curricula			University- industry interface(partnership)		Corporate Social responsibility	
	innovation	Change	adoption	seminar	entrepreneurship	To society	To environment
University name							
1.	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
2.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
3.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
4.	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
5.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
6.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
8.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
9.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Content Manifestation	100%	30%	100%	100%	80%	100%	90%

The name of PRME Participants of France

1. Ecole Superieur Robert de Sorbon, France
2. SKEMA Business School, France

3. CEMS, France
4. ICN Business School, France
5. Rouen Business School, France
6. EM Strasbourg Business School, France
7. Groupe Sup de Co Montpellier Business School, France
8. Toulouse Business School, France
9. BEM Bordeaux Management School, France
10. ESCP Europe, France

Table no-4 represents the line of action of some selected activities adopted by few of the selected Indian management institutes to pursue PRME principles. Through horizontal analysis in case of **change in curricula** we can find that in integrating three sub action(innovation, change & adoption) , only one institutes (no-3) integrated all thee, three institutes adopted (no-2,3 & 5)) adopted two actions and one institutes (no-1) adopted only one action. Whereas in **University- industry interface (partnership)** it states that only institute (no- 3) incorporated two actions and four institutes (no- 1, 2, 3& 5) implemented only one action. Similarly for **Corporate Social responsibility** two institutes (no- 3 & 4) incorporated two actions whereas two institutes incorporated only one action (no- 2 & 5) and one of reviewed institution incorporated none of the action.

Table no- 4

Country- India	Change in curricula			University- industry interface(partnership)		Corporate Social responsibility	
	innovation	Change	adoption	seminar	entrepreneurship	To society	To environment
University name							
1.	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
2.	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
3.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4.	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
5.	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
6.	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
7.	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
8.	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
9.	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
10.	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
Content Manifestations	60%	20%	100%	100%	10%	90%	50%

Through vertical analysis of actions, it can be assumed that only one among selected Indian management institutes(no- 3) integrated all seven actions (studied here), one institute (no-4) adopted five actions, two institutes (no-2 & 4) commenced four actions, one institutes (no-1) adopted two actions in order to follow PRME guidelines as participants.

The Names of PRME Participants from India:

1. Indian School of Business, India
2. National School of Leadership, India
3. Birla Institute of Management Technology, India
4. Institute of Productivity & Management, India
5. Indus Business Academy, India
6. VBS Purvanchal University, India
7. Prin. L.N. Welingkar Institute of Management Development and Research, India

8. Justice KS Hegde Institute of Management, India
9. S P Jain Institute of Management & Research, India
10. Aurous Institute of Management, India

Table no-5 represents the line of action of some selected activities adopted by few of the selected management institutes from USA to pursue PRME principles. Through horizontal analysis in case of **change in curricula** we can find that in integrating three sub action(innovation, change & adoption) , four institutes adopted (no-1,2,3 & 5) adopted two actions and one institutes(no-4) adopted only one action. Whereas in **University- industry interface (partnership)** it states that seven institutes (no- 3,4,5,6,7,8 &9) incorporated two actions and three institutes(no- 1,2 & 10) implemented only one action. Similarly for **Corporate Social responsibility** all five institutes (no- 1, 2, 3, 4&5) incorporated both two actions.

Through vertical analysis of actions, it can be assumed that only among selected management institutes from USA, four institutes (1, 2, 3&5) adopted six actions and one institutes (no-5) commenced five actions in order to follow PRME guidelines as participants.

Table no- 5

Country- USA	Change in curricula			University- industry interface(partnership)		Corporate Social responsibility	
	innovation	Change	adoption	seminar	entrepreneurship	To society	To environment
University name							
1.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
2.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
3.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
4.	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
5.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
6.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
8.	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
9.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Content Manifestation	90%	30%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

The Name of US-PRME Participants

1. Coles College of Business, USA
2. Marlboro College Graduate School, USA
3. Merrick School of Business, USA
4. Thunderbird School of Global Management, USA
5. Weather head School of Management, USA
6. Rollins College, USA
7. Villanova School of Business, USA
8. Joseph M. Katz Graduate School of Business & College of Business Administration, USA
9. The University of Vermont, USA
10. Daniels College of Business, USA

Findings

1. Global Status of Actions and Contents Supremacy under PRME- To understand the succinct status of actions as manifested by 45 numbers of the PRME participating institutions of 5 countries were compared in the table-6. Cent percent of France institutes followed by US Institute 9 percent, Brazil by 7 percent emphasized on curricula innovation. Change in respect to curricula are within 30 percent, but cent percent of institute of whole selected groups of institutes of selected 5 countries of the globe manifested the adoption of curricula. In the similar way, in case of organizing seminar for industry institute interaction, cent percent of institutes are manifesting that they organize it to achieve it. In case of emphasis on entrepreneurship as principle, cent percent of US institutes followed by France (80 percent) and by Brazil with 70 percent of institutes. Whereas, the 10 percent of Indian PRME registered institutes are manifesting entrepreneurship as a mean of university-institute interaction. An interesting revelation is that except the Indian institutes, the cent percent institute of other 4 countries is showing the social responsiveness by incorporating the direct contents under the social responsibility. The US and France management institutes are manifesting their commitment on environmentalism. 50 percent of Indian management institutes registered under PRME manifesting the commitment on environmentalism as a part of educational social responsibility (ESR). Thus, the table-6 revealed the supremacy of contents/action is adoption of curricula and seminar for university-industry interface as being mostly prioritized action lines under PRME. Second line of domination of the manifested contents of commitment to principle is the society followed by environment.

Table -6

Sl. No	Country	Change in Curricula			University-Industry Interface		Corporate Social Responsibility	
		Innovation	Change	Adoption	Seminar	Entrepreneurship	Society	Environment
1	Brazil (10)	7 (70%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)	7 (70%)	10 (100%)	7 (70%)
2	Japan (5)	1 (20%)	1 (20%)	5 (100%)	5 (100%)	2 (40%)	5 (100%)	5 (100%)
3	France (10)	10 (100%)	3 (30%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)	8 (80%)	10 (100%)	9 (90%)
4	India (10)	6 (60%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)	1 (10%)	9 (90%)	5 (50%)
5	USA (10)	9 (90%)	3 (30%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)	10 (100%)
Institutes' Actions / Content Supremacy		33 (73%)	11 (24%)	45 (100%)	45 (100%)	29 (64%)	43 (96%)	36 (80%)

It is interesting to note that content supremacy as revealed in the table does not make apparent the differences of two contents positive and negative association along with association or ties of actions undertaken by institutes in this study. For understanding the association and grouping of manifested contents actions an analysis for sign test was conducted by assuming the manifested contents of 45 institutions who submitted the PRME commitment of 5 different countries of the globe. To observe, association between three pairs of tied actions seminar(s) and curricula (CC), entrepreneurship (E) and Change in Curricula (CC), and environment (Env.) and finally Change in Curricula (CC). In the Table -7 reveals that 33 numbers out of 45 numbers of institute are showing negative difference of mutual existence of actions are of 12 numbers of institutes, i.e. 12 number of institutes of this sample have adopted seminar and curricula changes (S=CC=12). Entrepreneurship (E) and Change of Curricula among 41 numbers of institutes manifesting as negative difference and only 4 numbers of institutes are manifesting as they are adopting entrepreneurship and curricula change actions (E=CC=4). The social responsive (So) and curricula change (CC) are manifested negative distribution in the cases of 34 numbers out 45 institutes and only 11 numbers of institutes' commitment have shown ties (So=CC= 11). The commitment for environmentalism (Env) under CSR and Curricula

(CC) are negatively differentiated in case of commitment of 36 institutes (Env<33) and manifesting their ties of actions for environmentalism and change in curricula (Env=CC=09) only by 9 numbers of institutes of the total 45 institute in this sample.

Table-7

Frequencies for Sign Test (Ties of Actions)

Manifested Actions Ties	-- Difference	Positive Difference	Ties (T)	Rank T
	Total Numbers institutes (N=45)			
Seminar (S) and Change in Curricula (CC)	S<CC= 33	S>CC = 0	S=CC= 12	4
Entrepreneurship (E) and Curricula (CC)	E<CC= 41	E>CC= 0	E=CC=04	9
Society (So) and Curricula (CC)	So < CC=34	So >CC=0	So =CC= 11	5
Environment (Env) and Curricula ©	Env <CC= 36	Env> CC= 0	Env =CC=09	6
Innovation (I) and Industry-Institute Interaction (III)	I<III= 37	I>III=0	I=III= 08	7
Change(Ch) and Industry-Institute-Interaction (III)	Ch<III= 43	Ch>III= 0	Ch=III=02	10
Adoption (A) and Industry-Institute-Interaction (III)	A<III= 29	A>III= 0	A=III=16	3
Innovation (I) and Society (So)	I<So= 38	I>So= 0	I=So=07	8
Change (Ch) and Society (So)	Ch<So=44	Ch>So=0	Ch=So=01	11
Adoption (A) and Society (So)	A<So= 36	A>So= 1	A=So=08	7
Seminar(S) and Society (So)	S<So= 36	S>So= 1	S=So= 08	7
Entrepreneurship (En) and Society (So)	En<So= 41	En>So= 0	En=So= 04	9
Industry Institute Interaction (III) and Curricula (CC)	III<CC= 17	III>CC= 4	III=CC= 24	1
Society (So) and Industry-Institute Interactions (III)	So<III= 18	So>III= 9	So=III= 18	2

The next series of manifested association with dominant action, i.e. Industry Institute Interaction (III) with innovation (I), Change (Ch), Adoption (A) are analysed in the table-7. In the cases of selected institute here commitment for Industry Institute Interaction (III) with the commitment for innovation have manifested by negative difference I<III=33, whereas only in case of 8 numbers of institute concerned are manifesting the condition of mutual presence (I=III=8). With change in curricula (Ch) with industry institute interaction negatively distributed (Ch<III=43), they forms ties of action (Ch=III=2) in case of 2 institute, meaning hereby change in curricula and industry institute interaction manifesting that it does not go hand in hand. The adoption of curricula (A) and industry institute interaction (III) are negatively differentiated (A<III=29) and simultaneously the actions go hand in hand in case of 16 numbers of institutions (A=III=16). Next, series action manifestations are social concern (So) with innovation (I), Change (Ch), Adoption (A), Seminar (S). In this analysis, found that Innovation of Curricula (I) and society is negatively differentiated (I<So=38) and both the actions go hand in hand in (I=So=7) for seven institutes. Change in Curricula (Ch) and Social Orientation (So) are negatively differentiated (Ch<So=44) for cases and they forming the ties action at commitment only in one case i.e. (Ch=So=1). Adoption of Curricula(A) and social orientation is negatively differentiated (A<So=36) in case of 36 institutes, manifested the simultaneous action ties (A=So=8), and Positively differentiated (A>So=1) in case of only one institute. Social orientation (So) with seminar

(S) also negatively differentiating ($S < S_o = 36$); whereas, seminar and social orientation are showing manifested simultaneous action ties ($S = S_o = 8$) in case of eight institutes.

The next association are analysed are entrepreneurship (En) with the social orientation (So) which reflecting negative simultaneous differentiation ($En < S_o = 41$) for 41 numbers of institutions and the manifested simultaneous action ties ($En = S_o = 4$) i.e. only for 4 institutes. Industry institute interaction (III) and curricula (CC) manifested negatively differentiation ($III < CC = 17$) for 17 institutes, whereas, simultaneous action ties manifested for ($III = CC = 24$) 24 numbers of institute. Societal orientation (So) and industry institute interaction (III) are manifested negatively differentiated ($S_o < III = 18$) for 18 numbers of institutions, whereas reflected positive differentiation ($S_o > III = 9$) for nine institutes, and simultaneous action ties ($S_o = III = 18$) for 18 numbers of institutions.

2. Reflection of actions- After studying activities and actions adopted and carried out by some of the PRME participating B-Schools in Asia, Europe and South & North America thoroughly, it was found that there are contrasts in the line of actions in partaking to the PRME principles. This study analyses three major actions which contains five sub actions like innovation, adoption and change in curricula, organizing seminar and promoting entrepreneurship in Industry-university interface and corporate social responsibility to society and environment. The analysis revealed the beholder of manifested content supremacy actions for Adoption of Curricula, Organizing Seminar, and Actions for Societal Orientation, and finally Environmentalism under the commitment of business and management institutes of the select PRME participants of the five management education giant of the globe. The ranks of simultaneous or pair manifested actions industry institute interaction and curricula change ($III = CC = 24$), following by the societal responsiveness (So) with industry institute interaction (III). In the third rank, Industry Institute Interaction (III) and curricula adoption (A) manifested simultaneous actions of the select b-schools.

Scope of Future Work

The manifested content analysis on the commitment of PRME participants illuminates many interesting facts. The ties of simultaneous manifested action ties in case of industry institute interaction and curricula change is a global phenomenon in the context of management institutes. Unless the industry institute interacts there can't have curricula change vice versa. If an institute is socially responsive in their embedded commitment then only industry institute interaction would go simultaneously. Adoption of curricula and industry institute interaction goes hand in hand. Actions in regard to entrepreneurship and curricula change still not getting due attention in the context of the b-schools participating in PRME is a global symptom. Change in curricula and Industry institute interaction goes hand in hand but is no getting due consideration among the B-Schools of the globe. All these interesting findings manifested content analysis of documents can serve as the basis for further exploration at country level as well as global level. A global scale of research can be conducted for further clarification of the facts manifested by the study.

Conclusion

This study reflects a contrasted overview of actions for adopting different activities by the PRME participating management institutions in order to follow the follow international guideline of PRME in order to incorporate an inclusive and sustainable socio-economic development along with ecological sustainability. There are some disparities of action in both number and type of approach already integrated for building responsible future by business leaders who will not only believe in philanthropic attitude like CSR rather more responsible business leader for a better and brighter tomorrow.

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